

REACTIVE PROCESSING OF TEXTILE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

Hilde Parton, Ignaas Verpoest
*Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering,
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium*

ABSTRACT

The high melt viscosity of thermoplastics is the main issue when producing thermoplastic composites. For this reason, production methods for thermoplastic and thermoset composites differ substantially. Lowering the viscosity of thermoplastics to a value below 1 Pa.s enables the use of thermoset production methods such as Resin Transfer Moulding. In order to achieve these low viscosities, a low viscous mixture of prepolymers and catalyst can be infused into a mould, where the polymerisation reaction takes place. Only a number of polymerisation reactions are compatible with a closed mould process. These polymerisation reactions proceed rapidly compared to the curing reaction of thermosets used in RTM. Therefore, the processing window is narrow and managing the processing parameters is crucial. This paper describes the production and properties of a glass fibre reinforced polyester produced from cyclic oligoesters.

Key Terms: thermoplastics, reactive processing, processing window

INTRODUCTION

The advantages of thermoplastic matrices over their thermoset counterparts for use in composites are well known and include improved toughness and ease of recycling. The main problem when using thermoplastic matrices for composites is the difficulty of impregnating fibrous reinforcement with high viscosity resins. The processing techniques for thermoplastic composites can be divided into two main areas [1], processes that attempt to reduce the distance that the resin is required to flow and those that aim to reduce the viscosity. If the viscosity of thermoplastics can be lowered sufficiently, thermoset production techniques like Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) can be used with minor adaptations to process thermoplastic composites. Following conditions need to be fulfilled [2, 3]:

- the matrix viscosity during impregnation should be below 1 Pa.s,
- after impregnation, the matrix can be solidified chemically or physically in a sufficiently short time,
- the final matrix should have high enough mechanical properties.

In order to achieve a viscosity comparable to that of thermosets during processing, the molecular weight of the thermoplastic resin should be as low as possible. However, this low molecular weight would lead to poor mechanical and thermal properties. Another way to meet these conditions, is to inject a mixture of molten prepolymers (monomers or oligomers) with catalyst and/or activator into the mould where the polymerisation reaction takes place. Not all polymerisation reactions are suited for a closed mould process: by-products and side-reactions should be avoided, the reaction exotherm cannot be too large, and complete conversion must be accomplished in a reasonable timeframe and without purification. Anionic ring-opening polymerisation of polyamides and the entropically driven ring-opening polymerisation of cyclic oligoesters, fulfil these requirements.

Reaction injection moulding of short fibre reinforced polyamide 6 has been known and used for many years. Due to the higher residual monomer content and poor dimensional stability in the presence of moisture of polyamide 6, research on continuously reinforced polyamides has focussed on carbon fibre reinforced polyamide 12 [2, 4-6]. The main disadvantage of using polyamide 12, is the low reaction speed below the polymer melting point. Consequently, processing below the polymer melting point would lead to unacceptable cycle times. Therefore, thermal cycling of the mould cannot be avoided.

The production of cyclic oligomers as raw material for the production of polyesters is a recent development [7]. The ring-opening polymerisation of these cyclic oligoesters is suited for in-situ polymerisation. Compared to polyamide 12, the reaction exotherm is smaller and processing below the polymer melting point is possible without increasing the cycle time intolerably. Therefore, isothermal processing is feasible. There has not yet been a systematic study on the properties of composites with various fibre architectures although some work has been reported on carbon fibre reinforced materials [7-9]. This paper describes the production and properties of glass fibre reinforced composites made from cyclic oligoesters.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

The prepolymers used in this study were the cyclic butylene terephthalate oligomers (CBT™) supplied by Cyclics Corporation. These oligomers are precursors for the thermoplastic polybutylene terephthalate (PBT). The number of butylgroups in the oligomer mixture varies from two to seven, resulting in a melting range from 130-160 °C. Before processing, the oligomers were dried overnight at 110 °C to remove residual moisture, which could interfere with the polymerisation reaction. The tin-based catalyst (Fastcat™ 4101) is commercially available from Atofina Chemicals Incorporated.

The reinforcements used were a biaxial ($\pm 45^\circ$) non-crimp glass fibre fabric (602 g/m²) and a uni-directional non-crimp glass fibre fabric (951 g/m²) both supplied by Saertex Wagener GmbH. These fabrics were also dried overnight at 110 °C before processing.

Twintex® PBT from Vetrotex Reinforcement S.A. was used as a reference material.

2. Process

The process described in this paper is based on the RTM process, normally associated with thermoset composite production. The low viscous oligomer/catalyst mixture is vacuum infused into a closed mould (T_{mould}) containing the glass fibre textile reinforcement. The fundamental aspects of the processing method are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Reactive processing of thermoplastic composites

The oligomers are heated above their melting point (T_{melt}), the catalyst (0.45 wt%) is then added and the resulting mixture is stirred for a well-defined time (t_{stir}). During this time, polymerisation already commences, resulting in a continuously increasing viscosity and thus a limited time window for mould filling. Vacuum cannot be kept constant during the resin infusion. If the vacuum is too high, the low initial viscosity will lead to too fast mould filling leaving behind porosities in the fibre bundles. On the other hand, if the vacuum is too low, the high final viscosity will prevent complete mould filling. Therefore, vacuum (V_i) is increased incrementally from 0.4 to 0.8 bar with a step of 0.2 bar. Once the mould is completely filled (t_{fill}), in- and outlet ports are closed after which sufficient time (t_{dem}) should be available to complete the polymerisation reaction and cold crystallisation. The processing parameters used are described in Table 1 unless stated otherwise.

Table 1: Processing parameters

T_{melt} (°C)	190 ± 1
T_{mould} (°C)	190 ± 1
t_{stir} (s)	12
t_{dem} (min)	30

Flat plates ($320 \times 200 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$) with a fibre volume fraction between 40 and 60 % were successfully produced using the method described above.

3. Measurements

Molecular weight and molecular weight distribution: Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) is used to determine the molecular weight and its distribution. The measurements were performed with a mixture of chloroform/hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP) as solvent (98/2 $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{HFIP}$). The flow rate was 0.8 ml/min at a temperature of 20°C. Two Waters PL HFIPgel columns were used in series. The chromatograph was connected to Waters 484 UV detector working at 254 nm. In order to relate retention time to molecular weight, a universal calibration was made using various polystyrene standards. For sample preparation, approximately 2 mg of matrix was dissolved in 80 μl of HFIP. After total dissolution, the solution was diluted by 4 ml of chloroform. Samples containing glass fibres were filtered before injection. The number average (M_n) and weight average (M_w) molecular weight are defined as follows:

$$M_n = \frac{\sum_i n_i M_i}{\sum_i n_i} \quad \text{and} \quad M_w = \frac{\sum_i n_i M_i^2}{\sum_i n_i M_i} \quad 1.1$$

with n_i the number of moles with a mass M_i .

Conversion: Degree of conversion was determined from the GPC measurements and is calculated as follows:

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{A_{\text{oli}}}{A_{\text{tot}}} \quad 1.2$$

with α the degree of conversion, A_{oli} the area under the oligomer peaks of the retention time curve and A_{tot} the total area under the retention time curve.

Degree of crystallinity: Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) is used to measure crystallinity. Melting endotherms were recorded at 10 °C/min. The degree of crystallinity is defined as follows:

$$\chi_{c(\text{wt}\%)} = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_\infty} \quad 1.3$$

where ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy of the polymer, and ΔH_∞ is the melting enthalpy of the fully perfect crystal of PBT, which is found in literature to be 142 J/g [10]. In order to account for the fibres in the composite sample, the fibre weight fraction is determined by Thermogravimetical Analysis (TGA). The sample is heated from room temperature to 600 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Mechanical properties: The unidirectional composites as well as the polymerised CBT™ (pCBT) are tested in three point bending according to ASTM D790-84.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Production

Table 2 provides the mould filling times for different processing parameters. It is clear that the filling time is depending on both the melt temperature of the oligomer/catalyst mixture and the stirring time.

Table 2: Mould filing times

	plate 1	plate 2	plate 3
T_{melt} (°C)	191	191	186
T_{mould} (°C)	190	190	190
t_{stir} (s)	30	12	12
t_{fill} (s)	210	180	160

Increasing the stirring time (plate 1 versus plate 2), increases the initial conversion and thus the viscosity, which leads to a smaller time window for injection ($\eta < 1$ Pa·s). If the time window is too small for the vacuum profile applied, the mould is not completely filled as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Biaxially reinforced PBT

Decreasing the melt temperature on the other hand (plate 3 versus plate 2), decreases the reaction speed inside the vessel, resulting in a lower conversion at t_{stir} . A lower reaction speed results in a slower viscosity build-up and hence a larger time window. If the vacuum profile is not altered, a

lower reaction speed leads to a shorter filling time. The mould temperature was kept constant in these experiments, but this temperature will indisputably affect the filling time due to a change in the reaction speed.

2. Matrix properties

The degree of conversion, the molecular weight and the degree of crystallinity are all important characteristics for the mechanical properties of the matrix and consequently for the mechanical properties of the composite. Since the matrix is polymerised inside a closed mould and in the presence of glass fibres, these properties can vary from commercial PBT.

Figure 3: Molecular weight

Figure 3 shows the average molecular weight. The presence of fibres seems to lower the molecular weight, however, in comparison with the commercial Twintex®, the molecular weight is in the same order of magnitude. Although the decrease in molecular weight as a result of the fibre presence has to be further investigated, it is believed to be related to the fraction of material with very low retention time (t_{ret}) seen in the GPC measurements, Figure 4. This fraction can be partially crosslinked PBT, promoted by the reactive functions on the fibre sizing [10]. The crosslinked PBT has a very high molecular weight. This hypothesis will be confirmed with further research.

Figure 4: GPC data of UD reinforced PBT

Table 3 shows the degree of conversion, degree of crystallinity and melting point. The degree of conversion, as calculated by equation 1.2, seems to be lower when the CBT™ is polymerised in

the presence of fibres. These results can however be an underestimate of the real degree of conversion due to interference of the glass fibre sizing. As can be seen in Figure 5, the oligomer peaks at high retention time overlap with the peak related to the glass fibre sizing.

Table 3: Matrix properties derived from GPC (α) and DSC measurements (χ_c and T_m)

	α (%)	χ_c (%)	T_m (°C)
pCBT in DSC	/	38.9 ± 0.9	220.1 ± 0.4
pCBT in mould	98.3 ± 1.0	38.8 ± 4.8	222.5 ± 0.8
$\pm 45^\circ$	92.4 ± 2.3	32.1 ± 2.0	219.3 ± 0.8
UD	93.1 ± 2.1	33.6 ± 2.9	222.8 ± 1.1
Twintex	95.3 ± 0.8	/	/

Figure 5: Influence of fibre sizing

DSC measurements are used to determine the melting point as well as the degree of crystallisation. Figure 6 shows some typical DSC curves of pCBT. The first curve depicts pCBT polymerised at 220 °C inside the DSC, after which the sample was cooled at 10 °C/min. The double melting peak results from the melting and recrystallisation of imperfect crystals [11]. The appearance of multiple melting peaks would therefore be an indication of poor crystal quality in the composite part. This behavior is not seen in the melting curves of the UD composite parts polymerised at 190 °C. The resulting melting point and the degree of crystallinity as calculated by equation 1.3 are given in Table 3.

The degree of crystallinity is higher in the unreinforced PBT. This can be explained by the high molecular weight fraction (Figure 4), which will not crystallise. Further research is however necessary to confirm this.

Figure 6: Typical DSC curves for composite samples

3. Composite properties

The flexural modulus and strength of the pCBT matrix and UD composites are tested by three point bending, Table 4. Both the modulus and strength of the pCBT are comparable to the information provided by Cyclics Corporation. Three point bending tests on the UD composites are performed in both the fibre direction and the transverse direction. The transverse direction is tested in order to assess the matrix and interface properties.

The UD non-crimp fabric used, contains some 90° fibres, namely 27 g/m² compared to 912 g/m² in the 0°-direction. The classical laminate theory is used to calculate the stiffness. The theoretical longitudinal modulus of the composite is 39.5 GPa, whereas the theoretical transverse modulus is 10 GPa.

Insufficient input data were available to calculate the theoretical strength according to the classical laminate theory. Therefore, the 90° fibres were taken into account by homogenising the matrix with these fibres ($V_f = 3.4\%$). The theoretical longitudinal strength (calculated with a fibre strength of 1.5 GPa) is 850 MPa. The transversal strength is lower than the matrix strength due to the stress concentration around the fibres.

Table 4: Flexural properties from three point bending tests

	UD ($V_f = 54\%$)	Matrix	Datasheet
$E_{//}$ (GPa)	37.6 ± 1.3	E (GPa)	2.9 ± 0.2 2.4
E_{\perp} (GPa)	8.5 ± 0.9		
$\sigma_{//}$ (MPa)	775 ± 118	σ (MPa)	79 ± 3 80-115
σ_{\perp} (MPa)	66 ± 6		
$\epsilon_{//}$ (%)	2.3 ± 0.3	ϵ (%)	3.4 ± 0.2 /
ϵ_{\perp} (%)	2.0 ± 0.3		

Although some assumptions were made during the calculations, the predicted values are quite close to the experimental ones.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new production method to produce continuously reinforced thermoplastics was described. Due to the high reaction speed of the cyclic oligoesters, the time window for fibre impregnation is small and strongly depending on the processing parameters. Therefore, processing parameters need to be well-controlled in order to achieve reproducible parts.

The main matrix properties were investigated. Both the molecular weight and the degree of crystallinity decrease when fibres are present during polymerisation. Although further research is required, partially crosslinked PBT might be causing this decrease. The lower conversion of the composite matrix is an underestimate of the real conversion, since the glass fibre sizing interferes with the measurements.

The mechanical properties of both the matrix and the UD composite were tested. The results compared well to the theoretical values and the properties provided by the supplier.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Prof. J. Devaux from the Laboratoire des Hauts Polymères, Université Catholique de Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium for the use of their GPC equipment and the discussions. Thanks are also expressed to the FWO-Vlaanderen for funding this research as well as to the Amiterm project partners for supplying materials.

REFERENCES

1. Miller, A. and A.G. Gibson, *Impregnation techniques for thermoplastic matrix composites*. Polymers & Polymer Composites, 1996. **4**(7): p. 459-481.
2. Luisier, A., P.E. Bourban, and J.A.E. Manson, *Time-temperature-transformation diagram for reactive processing of polyamide 12*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 2001. **81**(4): p. 963-972.
3. Mairtin, P.O., et al., *Process investigation of a liquid PA-12/carbon fibre moulding system*. Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2001. **32**(7): p. 915-923.
4. Luisier, A., P.E. Bourban, and J.-A.E. Manson. *In-situ polymerisation of polyamide 12 for thermoplastic composites*. in *ICCM-12*. 1999. Paris. p. CD-rom paper 610
5. Zingraff, L., et al. *Reactive processing and forming of polyamide 12 thermoplastic composites*. in *23rd Sampe Europe Conference*. 2002. Paris. p. 237-248
6. Connor, T.C., et al. *EMS polymerisation moulding (EPM): A novel solution to thermoplastic composite manufacturing*. in *19th International SAMPE Europe Conference*. 1998. Paris. p. 385-395
7. Hall, A.J. and P. Hodge, *Recent research on the synthesis and applications of cyclic oligomers*. Reactive & Functional Polymers, 1999. **41**(1-3): p. 133-139.
8. Ciovacco, J. and S.J. Winckler. *Cyclic thermoplastic properties and processing*. in *Proceedings of the 45th International SAMPE Symposium*. 2000. Long Beach CA: Sampe Publishing

9. Rösch, M. and R.H.J. Eder. *Processing Cyclic Thermoplastic Polyester*. in *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Fibre Reinforced Composites*. 2002. Newcastle. p. 54-62
10. Vendramini, J., et al., *Commingled poly(butylene terephthalate)/unidirectional glass fiber composites: Influence of the process conditions on the microstructure of poly(butylene terephthalate)*. *Polymer Composites*, 2000. **21**(5): p. 724-733.
11. Nichols, M.E. and R.E. Robertson, *The Multiple Melting Endotherms From Poly (Butylene Terephthalate)*. *Journal of Polymer Science Part B-Polymer Physics*, 1992. **30**(7): p. 755-768.